

THE FUNDAMENTAL TYPES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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ELSEVIER

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Abstract: The origin of phraseology is the subject of this article. The authors of this article are attempting to define phraseology and distinguish it from lexicology. They first introduced the term phraseology to academics, who attempted to study phraseology, a subfield of linguistics, in order for them to comprehend it. It is abundantly clear that this subfield of linguistics is relatively new, and very few researchers have been able to comprehend the world that phraseology creates. This article examines the fundamental types of phraseological units and how much idiomaticity is involved in learning a foreign language. Using numerous examples, the authors attempted to define the various types of phraseological units.

Keywords: vocabulary, language, phraseology, study, stylistic, PU, word-group, style, origin, idiom, stability, phraseological fusions, phraseological unities, phraseological collocations.

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The study of set or fixed expressions, such as idioms, phrasal verbs, and other types of multi-word lexical units (often referred to collectively as phrasemes), in which the individual parts of the expression take on a meaning that is either more specific than, or otherwise not predictable from, the sum of their meanings when used independently, is known as phraseology in linguistics. For instance, the phrase "Dutch auction" is made up of the words "of or pertaining to the Netherlands" and "a public sale in which goods are sold to the highest bidder," but it does not mean "a sale in the Netherlands where goods are sold to the highest bidder" as the definition suggests; Instead, the term is commonly used to describe any auction in which prices fall rather than rise. History Phraseology is a scholarly approach to language that originated in the twentieth century. It is derived from the Greek words phrasis, which means "way of speaking," and -logia, which means "study of." Charles Bally's idea of locutions phraseology entered Russian lexicology and lexicography in the 1930s and 1940s, and it was later developed in the countries of the former Soviet Union and other Eastern European nations. It became established in East German linguistics at the end of the 1960s and was occasionally approached in English linguistics. The earliest English adaptations of phraseology are by Weinreich, Arnold, Lipka, and Arnold in the context of transformational grammar. Phraseology has been steadily developed over the past two decades in Great Britain and other Western European nations. European interest in phraseology is evidenced by the regular conventions and publications of the

European Association for Lexicography (EURALEX) and European Society of Phraseology (EUROPHRAS). Phraseology research in Europe is more active than in North America. Welte and Cowie & Howarth both include bibliographies of recent studies on English and general phraseology. Their bibliography is reproduced and carried on the internet and is a rich source of the most recent publications in the field.

In phraseology, the fundamental units of analysis are referred to as phrasemes or phraseological units. According to Prof. Kunin A.V. [citation needed], phraseological units are stable word-groups with partially or fully transferred meanings (such as "to kick the bucket," "Greek gift," "drink till all's blue," "drunk as a fiddler (drunk as a lord, as a boiled owl)", and "as mad as a hatter" A phraseological unit, as defined by Rosemarie Gläser, is a commonly used lexicalized, reproducible billexemic or polylexemic word group with relative syntactic and semantic stability, the potential to be idiomatized, the potential to carry connotations, and the potential to have an emphatic or intensifying function in a text.

The origin of phraseology is the subject of this article. The authors of this article are attempting to define phraseology and distinguish it from lexicology. They first introduced the term phraseology to academics, who attempted to study phraseology, a subfield of linguistics, in order for them to comprehend it. It is abundantly clear that this subfield of linguistics is relatively new, and very few researchers have been able to comprehend the world that phraseology creates. This article examines the fundamental types of phraseological units and how much idiomaticity is involved in learning a foreign language. Using numerous examples, the authors attempted to define the various types of phraseological units. The significance of expressiveness isn't derived from the worth of the amount of its components, not set in stone by reevaluating. This is on the grounds that the phraseological expression is certainly not a free expression, however one of its primary properties is reproducibility. So the free mixes are the articulations 'white snow', 'dark pen', 'yellow pencil', which are made from discrete words during the time spent correspondence, simultaneously, the articulations 'innocent embellishment', 'dark gold', 'underground market', 'yellow papers' are PU that are recovered from the memory very much like individual words. Any infringement in the syntactic or semantic design of these PU hopelessly prompts the deficiency of their significance. It has been over and again brought up that word-bunches dissected as practically and semantically indivisible units are viewed as the topic of style. It ought to be noticed that appropriate logical examination of English manner has not been endeavored until as of late. English and American language specialists attempted to gather different words, word-gatherings and sentences by introducing

a few elements of view, style, beginning and utilization which are curious to them. These units are typically depicted as maxims however no endeavor has been made to break down these phrases as a different class of phonetic units. Notwithstanding, the current terms, for example, set-phrases, colloquialisms, word-reciprocals reflect somewhat the vitally easy to refute issues of manner. The term set-state infers that the fundamental rule of separation is the steadiness of lexical parts and linguistic construction of word-gatherings. The term figures of speech by and large infer that the fundamental component of the semantic units viable is the idiomaticity or absence of inspiration.

Phraseological units are constantly characterized as non-spurred word-bunches that can't be unreservedly given up in discourse however are duplicated as an instant framework. This definition continues from the presumption that the fundamental highlights of phraseological units are viewed as the strength of the lexical parts. It is habitually accepted that dissimilar to parts of free word-bunches which might fluctuate because of the necessities of correspondence, expressions of phraseological units are replicated as single unchangeable collocations.

Considering predominantly the level of idiomaticity phraseological units might be arranged into three major gatherings: phraseological combinations, phraseological solidarities and phraseological collocations.

Phraseological combinations are totally non-propelled word-gatherings, like formality "regulatory techniques"; weighty dad "serious or grave part in a dramatic play"; die "bite the dust" and so forth. The significance of the parts has no associations at all, basically synchronically, with the importance of the entire gathering. Idiomaticity is, when in doubt, joined with complete strength of the lexical parts and the linguistic design of the combination.

Phraseological unities are partially non-motivated as their meaning can usually be perceived through the metaphoric meaning of the whole phraseological unit. For example, **to show one's teeth**, **to wash one's dirty linen in public** if interpreted as semantically motivated through the combined lexical meaning of the component words would naturally lead one to understand these in their literal meaning. The metaphoric meaning of the whole unit, however, readily suggests '**take a threatening tone**' or '**show an intention to injure**' for *show one's teeth* and '**discuss or make public one's quarrels**' for *wash one's dirty linen in public*. Phraseological unities are as a rule marked by a comparatively high degree of stability of the lexical components.

Phraseological collocations are motivated but they are made up of words possessing specific lexical valency which accounts for a certain degree of stability in such word-groups. In phraseological collocations variability of member words is strictly limited. For instance, **bear a grudge** may be changed into **bear malice**,

but **not intobear a fancy or liking**. We can say **take a liking(fancy)** but **not take hatred (disgust)**. These habitual collocations tend to become kind of clichés where the meaning of member-words is to some extent dominated by the meaning of the whole group. Due to these phraseological collocations are felt possessing a certain degree of semantic inseparability.

To conclude the article, it can be reviewed that by taking into consideration the degree of idiomaticity phraseological units are classified into three groups such as phraseological fusions, phraseological unities and phraseological collocations. They are differentiated according to their idiomaticity and they are proven with the examples.

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